

GRZEGORZ GIERLASIŃSKI¹

Nabis larvatus (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Nabidae): new records of apterous damsel bug from New Caledonia

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14898430>

¹ Natural History Collections, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Uniwersytetu Poznańskiego 6, 61-614 Poznań, Poland, e-mail: ggierlas@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-2968-8553

² rue Alfred de Musset, 98800 Noumea, New Caledonia, e-mail: damien.brouste@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0001-7116-2072

³ Institute of Biology, Biotechnology and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Silesia in Katowice, Bankowa 9, 40-007 Katowice, Poland, e-mail: artur.taszakowski@us.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-0885-353X

Abstract: *Nabis* (*Australonabis*) *larvatus* KERZHNER, 1970 (Nabidae: Nabinae: Nabini), is the only known apterous representative of the family. Wing reduction is accompanied by the absence of ocelli, reduced and forward-shifted eyes, a shortened posterior lobe of the pronotum, and the presence of sharp projections on the pronotum. New localities and high-resolution photographs of *Nabis larvatus* are presented in the paper.

Key words: biodiversity, damsel bugs, Heteroptera, hot spot, taxonomy, true bugs.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Nabis* LATREILLE, 1802 is the most numerous genus of damsel bugs, represented in the world's fauna by nearly one hundred species present on all continents except Antarctica (GBIF 2025). Representatives of this genus, like most taxa of the family Nabidae, are predators of small arthropods (SCHUH & WEIRAUCH 2020). The genus *Nabis* acts as a dumping ground for most of the Nabini because of the similarity in the general appearance of most taxa (KERZHNER 1981, PÉRICART 1987, KIM *et al.* 2021).

Nabis (*Australonabis*) *larvatus* KERZHNER, 1970, is one of the most peculiar representatives of damsel bugs. It is characterized by the complete reduction of wings, making it the only known family member with such an advanced loss of flight organs. This reduction is accompanied by the absence of ocelli, reduced and forward-shifted eyes, a shortened posterior lobe of the pronotum, and the presence of sharp projections on the anterior lobe of the pronotum (KERZHNER 1970).

This species is endemic to New Caledonia and was described only in the second half of the 20th century, despite material from this region being previously studied by DISTANT (1920). Most likely, the peculiar nymph-like appearance of this species contributed to its neglect in the earlier works.

The existing data on the occurrence of this species in New Caledonia is limited to general references to the central part of the island and the summit of Mt. St. Arago (KERZHNER 1970).

The present paper gives new localities of this species based on museum collections and direct field observations conducted by the second author. High-resolution photographs of *Nabis larvatus* are also given.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The photographs of specimens from museum collections were taken in the Laboratory of Insect Anatomy and Morphology of the Institute of Biology, Biotechnology and Environmental Protection, the University of Silesia in Katowice (Katowice, Poland). The focus-stacked colour photographs were prepared with a Leica M205C stereo microscope with a high diffuse dome illumination Leica LED5000 HDI, Leica Flexacam C3 digital camera, and LasX ver. 5.1.025593 software.

Images were combined using the Image Composite Editor (panoramic image stitcher). The figures were prepared using Adobe Photoshop 2025 graphic editor.

Detailed label data are cited in their original form. A backward slash (\) separates the rows on the label, and a double backslash (\\) separates individual labels. The material examined is deposited in the following collections:

BMNH The Natural History Museum (London, United Kingdom);
USMB Upper Silesian Museum (Bytom, Poland).

RESULTS

Taxonomy:

Family: Nabidae A. COSTA, 1853

Subfamily: Nabinae A. COSTA, 1853

Tribe: Nabini A. COSTA, 1853

Genus: *Nabis* LATREILLE, 1802

Subgenus: *Australonabis* STROMMER, 1988

Species: *Nabis (Australonabis) larvatus* KERZHNER, 1970

Nabis larvatus KERZHNER, 1970: 349–350 (description, male genitalia).

Nabis (Australonabis) larvatus: STROMMER (1988): 80 (subgeneric placement).

Material examined.

Museum specimens (Fig. 1): ♂, “NEW CALEDONIA, PR.SUD _ 15 KM NE NOUMEA \ FOREST OF MTS KOGHIS \ 05.-06.03.2009 500 M. \ A. KUDRNA JR. LGT. \\ BMNH {E} \ 2009-12 \ A. Kudrna \\ NHMUKO15981874” (BMNH); ♂, same data, NHMUKO15981876 (BMNH); ♀, same data, NHMUKO15981875 (BMNH); 1 nymph, same data, NHMUKO15981873 (BMNH); ♀, “NEW CALEDONIA (S) \ 22°01.9'S 166°28.0'E \ Dzumac Mts, 900 m \ (Mt Ouin road junction) \ 29.12.2006 at light \ leg.R. Dobosz & M. Wanat” \\ 5915/4437 \\ MB0408343 (USMB); 1 nymph, same data, 5915/4431, MB0407423 (USMB); 1 nymph, same data, 5915/4360, MB0408215 (USMB); 1 nymph, “NEW CALEDONIA (S) \ 22°04.9'S 166°26.8'E \ Dzumac Road (S of Mts \ Couvélé road junction) \ 29.12.2006 700-800 m \ leg. R. Dobosz ” \\ 5915/4236 \\ MB0408343 (USMB);

♂, “NEW CALEDONIA (S) \ 22°10.7’S 166°30.4’E \ Mt Koghi, 450-500 m, \ 16.12.2006, rainforest, netting \ leg. R. Dobosz” \ 5915/5933 \ MB0407423 (USMB); ♂, same data, 5915/5934, MB0407423 (USMB); ♂, same data, 5915/5904, MB0407423 (USMB); 1 nymph, same data, 5915/5946, MB0407423 (USMB); 1 nymph, same data, 5915/5928, MB0407423 (USMB); 1 nymph, same data, 5915/5958, MB0407423 (USMB); 1 nymph, same data, 5915/2850, MB0407423 (USMB); ♀, “NEW CALEDONIA (S) \ 22°05.9’S 166°39.2’E \ Rivière Bleue Parc 185 m \ 1 km E of scient. refuge \ 22.12.2006 humid forest \ leg. R. Dobosz & M. Wanat” \ 5915/25875 \ MB0408343 (USMB).

Field observations (Fig. 2). ♀, New Caledonia, Sud, Dumbéa, Les Koghis, -22.1774091082, 166.5081041671, 2 Oct 2020; ♀, same location, 11 Jul 2019; ♀, same location, 30 Apr 2019; ♀, same location, 19 Mar 2019; ♀, New Caledonia, Sud, Boulouparis, Humboldt rainforest, -21.8820150287, 166.4031074639, 16 Nov 2019; ♂, New Caledonia, Sud, Païta, Dzumac, -22.0820118382, 166.4379092665, 14 Sep 2019. The above-mentioned specimens were observed by Damien Brouste.

Biology:

The habitat of *Nabis larvatus* is the rainforest, where individuals are observed throughout the year, indicating this species' lack of seasonality. The observation times and the finding of one of the specimens in a ground light trap indicate a nocturnal lifestyle.

Distribution:

Nabis larvatus is a New Caledonian endemic. Locus typicus of this species is located in the central part of the island (the summit of Mt. St. Arago), but all the localities we present come from the southern part of New Caledonia.

Fig. 1. *Nabis larvatus* KERZHNER, 1970, NHMUKO15981876, ♂, A. dorsal view, B. antero-dorso-lateral view, C. lateral view.

Fig. 2. *Nabis larvatus* KERZHNER, 1970, females in natural habitat (photo by Damien Brouste).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are greatly indebted to Diana Isabel Rendón-Mera (The Natural History Museum in London) and Roland Dobosz (Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom) for a loan of the material.

FUNDING

The research activities were co-financed by the funds granted under the Research Excellence Initiative of the University of Silesia in Katowice.

REFERENCES

- DISTANT W. 1920. Rhynchota from New Caledonia. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (9)6: 143–194.
- GBIF 2025. <https://www.gbif.org/species/2020976>, access 2.01.2025.
- KERZHNER I.M. 1970. Neue und wenig bekannte Nabidae (Heteroptera) aus den tropischen Gebieten der Alten Welt. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 38(1969): 279–359.
- KERZHNER I.M. 1981. Poluzhestkokrylye semeystva Nabidae. Fauna SSSR, Nasekomye khobotnye, 13. Nauka, Leningrad, 326 pp.
- KIM J., ROCA-CUSACHS M., JUNG S. 2021. Molecular phylogeny of Nabidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Cimicomorpha): insight into relationships and reclassification with the proposal of the new tribe Stenonabini. *Systematic Entomology* 47(1): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/syen.12512>
- LATREILLE P.A. 1802. Histoire naturelle, générale et particulière des crustacés et des insectes. Paris, F. Dufart, An X-XIII., 467 pp.
- PÉRICART J. 1987. Hemipteres Nabidae d'Europe Occidentale et du Maghreb. Faune de France 71, I–XI, 1–185.
- SCHUH R., WEIRAUCH C. 2020. True bugs of the World (Hemiptera: Heteroptera). Classification and natural history (second edition). Siri Scientific Press, Manchester: 768 pp. + 32 pls.
- STROMMER N.G. 1988. Genera *Nabis* LATREILLE and *Stenonabis* REUTER (Hemiptera: Nabidae) in Australia. *Records of the South Australian Museum* 22: 79–93.

Accepted: 15 February 2025; published: 20 February 2025

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution License <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>